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Terrorism and the application of special criminal laws in handling cases

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Abstract

Laws and regulations like Law Number 5 of 2018 provide a solid legal foundation, but the research finds that there are still problems with effective cooperation between intelligence agencies and law enforcement when it comes to execution. By providing the scholarly groundwork to back up required regulatory modifications or adjustments, this study's results also contribute to the growth of Indonesian law and public policy. In order to build a more robust legal system and provide society with more comprehensive protection, the findings of this research may assist policymakers in developing more responsive and adaptable ways to cope with the terrorist threat. Research on the causes of terrorism, its effects on the economy, the efficacy of counterterrorism efforts, the patterns of terrorist attacks, and the connection between liberal democracies and terrorism are all part of this category. Differentiating between domestic and international terrorism has been a focal point of recent field advancements.

Keywords: Counter, terrorism, effectiveness, domestic, transnational, economic, juridic, eradication, crime of terrorism

Introduction

Suicide bombs and armed assaults are examples of how extremist organizations' methods have evolved in response to pressure from global terrorist networks. Concerns about national security, political instability caused by conflicts between anti-terrorism efforts and civil freedoms, and an increase in social anxiety and distrust are just a few areas where this surge in occurrences has had a noticeable influence. Education, tight surveillance, and increasing international collaboration in the fight against terrorism are all necessary responses to this danger, which necessitates that governments and communities maintain a state of constant adaptation.

Investigations, arrests, and protection against terrorist threats are all aspects of direct law enforcement that are under the purview of the police. For the purposes of deradicalization, countermeasures, and strategic coordination, BNPT develops policies. The gathering and analysis of data that forms the foundation for enforcement and prevention efforts is a crucial function of intelligence agencies (Aden, 2018) ^[6]. Collaboration between these organizations is crucial, since their combined efforts guarantee a rapid and efficient reaction to the danger of

terrorism. Terrorism is a worldwide danger that necessitates the transmission of information, coordination of operations, and diplomatic backing on a global scale; as a result, international cooperation is vital in both preventing and responding to terrorist attacks.

Literature Review

Wilt (2019) ^[5] To better understand the possible roadblocks to international legal cooperation in the battle against terrorism and organized crime is the primary objective of this article. Considering how closely related crime and terrorism are, it is believed that any effort to curb one kind of crime in that region will always have unintended consequences for the other. We will examine extraterritorial jurisdiction and international collaboration in criminal proceedings after discussing the vague notion of terrorism and its link to organized crime. We shall make few last points in the last part.

Macdonald, Stuart. (2015) ^[4] The consistency of precursor offences with the harm principle, the main theory of criminalization, is examined in this chapter's first section. To justify criminal liability for "remote harms" (i.e., activities like information gathering, training, and

fundraising) the burden of proof must be that the defendant had some normative involvement in the feared eventual harm, rather than that the defendant directly caused the harm. There are a lot of antecedent offenses that go beyond this limitation, too. This chapter contends that the idea of enemy criminal law may help us make sense of this. The goal of enemy criminal law is to deter future violence by targeting a certain group of dangerous criminals with harsh punishments and limited access to due process. The threat that foreign criminal law may infiltrate and taint our domestic criminal law is a major theme of this chapter. Furthermore, many common law countries need criminal justice responses to terrorism, but adversary criminal law might undercut the legitimacy and moral authority of such responses.

Mareček, Lukáš. (2017) ^[3]. In its interlocutory ruling on the relevant legislation, the Special Tribunal for Lebanon stated its stance on the problem of terrorism. In this essay, the author examines the significance of this concept in connection to Lebanese law, the motivation for its introduction, and the definition of unique crime. In light of the many experts who have criticized this ruling, this article seeks to ascertain the stance taken by the Special Tribunal for Lebanon (STL) and evaluate it in order to ascertain the validity and soundness of the STL's reasons. Final goals include determining the impact of the decision on the Special Tribunal for Lebanon's deliberations and on the development of international criminal law and the international criminal court.

Kwang (2017) ^[2] The constant threat of terrorism has prompted a realignment of criminal law standards with the primary goal of reducing terrorism. This article goes on to say that the idea of these new anti-terror statutes was not without merit. The first is that the substantive offenses that exist in the law are insufficient to apprehend all acts of terrorism. Second, unlike regular crimes, terrorist offenses may necessitate an extraordinary approach and treatment; third, the government wants to make it much easier to get convictions against terrorists, which is why these extraordinary offenses were created. The potential for unjust convictions due to a loosening of standards in criminal law, such as requirements of evidence, is a major worry for opponents. In this piece, we'll take a look at the current trend toward expanding anti-terror legislation' powers while ignoring the conventional norms and processes of criminal law.

Cancio Meliá, Manuel. (2011) ^[1]. The apex of Western criminal law systems' developmental ladder is terrorism. A genuine "criminal law" for adversaries seems to be on the horizon of penal legislation, which goes against many of the fundamental pillars of Western criminal law. The central claim is that the criminal justice system may be a powerful tool in the war against terrorism. This, however, exaggerates the preventative power of the criminal system, as any careful examination would show. In fact, a criminal overreaction could be counterproductive to the goal of countering terrorism, considering the communication strategy inherent in the crime. This is especially true because, while it offers no practical solution in terms of prevention, it could lead to a contamination effect that alters the constitutional underpinnings of the criminal justice system as a whole.

Countermeasures carried out by the police in handling terrorism crimes

The Regional Police combat non-criminal acts of terrorism by:

1. **Pre-emptive:** Given the critical nature of community leaders' roles, it is imperative that POLMAS (Community Police) be implemented with a convincing manner. It is believed that local leaders will be able to rally their communities to combat terrorism.
2. **Preventively:** The primary goal of early preventive efforts including integrated intelligence operations is to discover terrorist action plans. This opens the door for preventative actions to foil terror plots, saving lives and property.
3. **Repressively:** The goal of the National Police's repressive counterterrorism efforts is to put an end to terrorist attacks and bring those responsible to justice by the use of force. Following a credible threat or act of terror, certain coercive actions are often taken, including the apprehending of the offender, the search of the organization's headquarters, and the seizure of evidence like explosives or weapons. Special teams, like the 88th Anti-Terror Special Detachment, are responsible for carrying out these missions. This unit has the tactical ability necessary to cope with difficult circumstances and secure sites that may be terrorist targets.

Another kind of oppressive action carried out by the National Police is the enforcement of laws against terrorists via the judicial system. Following the suspect's arrest, the National Police and the prosecutor worked together to file an indictment and finally put the terrorist case to trial. Terrorists will face just punishment in line with the law, which is why this action is being taken. Therefore, in order to discourage the criminals and prevent other acts of terrorism, a rigorous judicial procedure is essential. As part of its repressive actions, the National Police froze assets and funds linked to terrorist networks, in addition to making arrests and pursuing legal processes. In order to trace and stop the transfer of money that may be used to finance terrorist operations, we work together with local and international financial institutions. This step is intended to disrupt the financial support system of terrorist organizations, denying them the means to plot or execute terrorist attacks.

The growth of terrorist networks in many nations, including Indonesia, highlights the critical need for intelligence and associated agencies to cooperate together in the fight against terrorism. In order to accomplish this synergy, it is important to work on enhancing links between different institutions by:

1. Using cutting-edge tech for monitoring and intercepting;
2. Infiltrating terrorist cells;
3. Creating early detection systems;
4. Sharing intelligence with other nations;
5. Building databases pertaining to terrorism; and
6. Prompt identification of catalysts for SARA-based animosity and hate against certain religious or national groups or countries.

For the purpose of maintaining peace and security in the country, the Indonesian government has delegated information gathering and analysis to the State information Agency (BIN). BIN plays a crucial role in gathering, evaluating, and communicating data pertaining to domestic and international threats to the state. Terrorism, espionage, subversion, and social disputes are just a few examples of the kinds of dangers that this agency keeps a look out for on behalf of the government. The Bureau of Intelligence and Research (BIN) works with other government organizations across the world to improve intelligence and information networks in order to counteract and avoid any dangers to the country. With strategic power to take preventative actions to safeguard national interests, BIN, the principal intelligence agency, works in close conjunction with the President and acts under his direct supervision. As a result, Densus 88 AT Polri must choose its own operating requirements. In order to begin an investigation, it is necessary to have accurate intelligence information in order to generate preliminary evidence.

Authorities may conduct well-informed arrests and detentions based on this knowledge. Also, intelligence reports help clarify things so that arrests aren't abused and that the facts used as preliminary proof are real and not made up. According to Article 28 of Perpu No. 1 of 2002, which states that investigators can arrest individuals strongly suspected of being involved in terrorism crimes based on preliminary evidence, this is crucial to ensure that the investigation process is not skewed by unlawful interests. In most cases, intelligence reports are the primary sources for this early information.

The use of law enforcement must be methodical and coordinated according to Law No. 8 of 1981 (KUHAP). When people work together in the field of criminal law, it indicates that they have common goals, perspectives, and strategies for reducing and eliminating crime. Unless the many parts of the criminal justice system work together and prioritize the system's interests, no part of the system will be able to successfully eradicate crime.

Law enforcement for special criminal cases on terrorism

Investigation, prosecution, and trial examination are all parts of the law enforcement procedure that go into enforcing the criminal offense of terrorism. It is the Criminal Procedure Code that governs these phases. Every law enforcement official is responsible for carrying out their assigned stage of the criminal justice process, yet all of the aforementioned stages function as interdependent units.

Investigating and inquiring are the steps used by law enforcement in a criminal justice system. When anything happens that seems like it may be a crime, it's crucial to have an investigator look into it. In order to establish guilt or innocence, identify a suspect, or both, an investigator has to be able to establish a case position.

State organs with the power to investigate and gather information in order to bring illegal conduct to light are known as investigators. Investigators are Republic of Indonesia police personnel or certain public servant officials with unique legal capacity to conduct investigations, according to Article 1 number (1) of Law Number 8 of 1981, which deals with the Criminal Procedure Law. The Republic of Indonesia's police officers and other

government employees with certain legal powers are designated as investigators under Article 6 of the Criminal Procedure Code.

There is a clear distinction between the responsibilities of an investigator and the process of inquiry itself. An investigation of a possible act of terrorism or circumstances suggesting such an act include a sequence of steps to identify and gather relevant information. In order to ascertain if the occurrence may be examined, searches are conducted for and attempts are made to locate incidents that are believed to be terroristic. Accordingly, investigations into alleged terrorist crimes may begin without delay upon receipt of such a complaint.

From an economic perspective, after the police have finished their investigation, the case is sent to the prosecutor's office for further processing and eventual court examination: At the court hearing, there are multiple steps to the examination process, including verifying the defendant's identity in accordance with Article 155 of the Criminal Procedure Code, advising and warning the defendant to pay attention, reading the indictment, asking the defendant if he or she understands it, and finally, obtaining the right to object or make an exception to the court process.

Particular rules pertaining to judicial examinations are outlined in Article 35 paragraph (1) of the Law on the Eradication of Criminal Acts of Terrorism, namely:

"If the defendant has been duly summoned and fails to appear in court without a legitimate justification, the case may be adjudicated in their absence."

The stipulations in the aforementioned article diverge from those in the Criminal Procedure Code, which mandates the defendant's presence throughout the court examination procedure. This clause is governed by Article 196, paragraph (1), which states that the court adjudicates matters in the defendant's presence, unless otherwise stipulated by law.

Law enforcement agencies and prosecutors are meticulously governed by criminal procedural law; however, the enforcement of laws against terrorist acts is a proactive measure aimed at countering intentional acts of violence or threats thereof that instill widespread terror or fear among the populace, resulting in mass casualties, deprivation of freedom, loss of life and property, and damage to critical infrastructure, the environment, public amenities, and international facilities.

Consequently, it is imperative to establish and enforce safeguards for investigators, public prosecutors, judges, correctional officers, and their families in instances of terrorist criminal acts, ensuring state protection against potential threats to their persons, lives, and/or properties throughout the entirety of the case examination process.

How has terrorism changed since 1968?

As event statistics are limited to 1968 and onwards, any analysis of terrorist trends must commence from that year. Terrorism statistics reveal distinct cycles characterized by frequent peaks and troughs associated with various attack methods, as terrorists and their governmental opponents react to one other's countermeasures. Generally, more intricate assault methods, such as skyjackings, have longer cycles compared to simpler methods, such as threats,

hoaxes, or explosions. Bombings, including various forms of assaults such as mail bombs, explosion bombings, and automobile bombings, are characterized by several cycles of differing durations. Understanding these cycles enables law enforcement personnel to predict future assaults when the patterns are consistent.

Transnational terrorist attacks increased from 1968 until the mid-1980s, reaching around 500 events annually, as seen in Figure 1 based on ITERATE statistics. The 1980s represented the era of state-sponsored terrorism (Hoffman, 2006). Following the mid-1990s, the frequency of transnational terrorist acts declined sharply to about 100 to 200 occurrences annually. This downturn is related to the reduction in governmental funding and the decrease in left-wing terrorism. Figure 2 illustrates the ratio of transnational and domestic terrorist incidents resulting in casualties (i.e., fatalities and/or injuries), derived from ITERATE and GTD, respectively. Three Transnational terrorism has shown an increasing incidence of deaths since 1997, correlating with the ascendance of religious fundamentalist terrorists who aimed for heightened destruction (Enders & Sandler, 2000; Rapoport, 2004) [11]. Prior to 1990, 26% of transnational

terrorist acts culminated in casualties; subsequent to 1990, 41% of these assaults resulted in fatalities. According to Enders, Sandler, and Gaibulloev's (2011) [12] categorization of GTD data, Figure 2 illustrates an increasing trend in the percentage of domestic terrorist incidents resulting in fatalities from 1989 to 2005. The ratio of domestic terrorist strikes resulting in casualties consistently exceeds that of international terrorist attacks involving casualties. Furthermore, domestic terrorist occurrences exceed international terrorist incidents by a factor of four to ten, depending upon the dataset and time frame examined.

A notable trend emerges from the selection of targets by terrorists. Assume that targets are classified into four primary categories: authorities, military, business, and private entities. (derived from ITERATE) illustrates that transnational terrorists have systematically adjusted their targeting strategies in response to security measures. As governmental leaders received security, international terrorists increasingly targeted vulnerable corporate entities in the 1970s. As enterprises safeguarded their assets, terrorists transitioned to targeting private gatherings.

Fig 1: Number of transnational terrorist incidents (ITERATE), 1968–2011

Fig 2: Proportion of transnational and domestic terrorist events with casualties

In 1980, terrorist assaults exceeded business attacks (Brandt & Sandler, 2010, 2012) ^[13, 14]. By 1999, terrorist assaults on private individuals exceeded those aimed at authorities. Domestic terrorism had a similar although accelerated evolution across target categories, with assaults on private individuals surpassing those on authorities by 1981, resulting in an ever-widening disparity afterward (Gaibulloev, Sandler & Santifort, 2012: 141) ^[14]. Post-1990s, a troubling trend emerged whereby terrorists increasingly targeted individuals rather than property (Brandt & Sandler, 2010, 2012) ^[13, 14]. This is likely attributable to two factors: (i) individuals represent a more vulnerable target, and (ii) religious fundamentalist terrorists aim for a higher number of victims. These tendencies in terrorist attacks help guide governments in the allocation of their limited counterterrorism resources.

Conclusion

The report emphasizes the need for a holistic and sustainable strategy to address terrorism-related offenses in Indonesia, concentrating on legal dimensions and inter-institutional cooperation. Notwithstanding the robust legal foundation established by Law Number 5 of 2018, execution continues to encounter obstacles. Recommendations include enhancing the capabilities of law enforcement and intelligence organizations to detect and address terrorist threats, strengthening international collaboration, and engaging the community in preventive initiatives via education and awareness. This essay illustrates that the analytical examination of terrorism is a highly dynamic research domain with significant policy implications. Event databases enabled empirical examinations of theoretical ideas, although highlighted a significant shortcoming: the need for data about governments' counterterrorism measures. While there exist some country-specific counterterrorism databases (e.g., Dugan & Chenoweth, 2012), a comprehensive global counterterrorism dataset is absent. This article emphasizes certain domains of significant new advancements and prospective research trajectories.

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